

First records of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in Morocco

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ABSTRACT: The first records of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) for Morocco are reported. Information on the known distribution of this species, mainly present in the Mediterranean Region, is summarized.

KEYWORDS: *Sphedanolestes pulchellus*, first records, distribution, Morocco, Mediterranean Region.

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The genus *Sphedanolestes* Stål, 1867 belongs to the subfamily Harpactorinae of the Reduviidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera). So far, *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) has been reported from Albania, Bosnia and Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Greece, Italy (Sardinia), North Macedonia, Turkey (European part) in Europe, Algeria, Egypt in North Africa and Cyprus, Iran, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey (Asian part) and Yemen in Asia (Putshkov & Putshkov, 1996; Protić, 1998; Putshkov & Moulet, 2009; Dursun & Salur, 2013; Najmeh et al., 2020; Aukema, 2022). The distribution area of this species has been expanded, as specimens of *S. pulchellus* were found in Morocco: On 08.02.2016 and on 24.06.2020, Alain Roujas photographed specimens of *S. pulchellus* near the village of Sidi R'bat, located in the region Souss-Massa at the Atlantic coast of Morocco (Figs. 1 and 2).

Photos of both specimens were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Roujas, 2022a, 2022b).

Likely, *S. pulchellus* reached Morocco by passive transport; possibly by ship from a Mediterranean port.

As *S. pulchellus* has not been reported for Morocco in scientific publications yet, the records reported in this note are the first ones for this country.

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830), near Sidi R'Bat, Souss-Massa, Morocco, 08.02.2016. (Photo: Alain Roujas).

Figure 2. Specimen of *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830), near Sidi R'Bat, Souss-Massa, Morocco, 24.06.2020. (Photo: Alain Roujas).